

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING VOCABULARY TO PRE-SCHOOL AND SCHOOL CHILDREN.

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Abstract. *This research work gives general information about methods and techniques of teaching vocabulary with increasing students interests in the lesson. Nobody can deny that increasing vocabulary is an essential part of our life and realizing its importance in language acquisition is a key to academic success in language learning. In addition to this, without vocabulary knowledge any language skill cannot be developed. Teaching vocabulary plays a pivotal role in the learning of a new foreign language and increasing word knowledge is a dynamic and meaningful way to develop it. Recent researches found it that nowadays, more and more students have problems with learning vocabulary because of not having exact and suitable strategies to learn it. Especially, second language learners cannot manage with vocabulary. They face with some problems due to only memorizing the words in different contexts and the words they heard. Also, they are not confident about with what methods they can learn effectively.*

Keywords: *Different type of methods and techniques, words, expressions, interesting and useful activities, increasing knowledge.*

Vocabulary is crucial for everyone who wants to learn a language in their life. “Vocabulary, as one of the knowledge areas in language, plays a great role for learners in acquiring a language” (Cameron, 2001). Without developing it, almost no one can achieve success in language learning. In other words, as Harmon, Wood & Keser (2009) as well as Linse (2005) mentioned that “Vocabulary is an important aspect of their language development.” Therefore, teachers should understand its importance if they want that their students will achieve academic success in the language learning.

Animals. Animal characteristics.

➤ In pairs, match each animal with the adjective which is traditionally used to describe them. (Re-order the adjectives when you write them up on the board; they appear here in the correct order.)

Owl, fox, mouse, monkey, lion, dog,
bat, ox donkey, dinosaur, pig, cat, fish,

Wise, clever, small, cheeky,
proud, loyal, blind, strong, stubborn,
extinct, greedy, independent, slippery

How do they compare with popular ideas about animals in your country,
e.g. Is an owl considered wise?

➤ Think of animals that these adjectives could describe.

Lazy, thoughtful selfish, kind, sensible, sensitive, posh, cold, cheerful, impatient, hard-working, easy-going, stylish, reserved, antisocial, moody

Think of another adjective to describe each animal and explain why you choose it.

Definitions.

➤ Choose five of these animals and write two sentences about each, one with *are* and one with *can*. Don't write the name of the animal, e.g. *They are covered in feathers*. *Most of them can fly*(birds).

Bees, hippopotamuses, horses, whales, snakes, spiders, owis, bats, ostriches, monkeys, cats, dogs, butterflies

In small groups, read your sentences to the others and see if they can guess the animal.

➤ Work in pairs. Imagine you are an animal, but don't tell your partner which one. Continue these sentences and see if your partner can guess what you are.

I live in... I'm afraid of... During the day I... I normally live for...
At night I ... I can... I eat... ...are afraid of me.

➤ Work in small groups. Give definitions of these groups of animals, and write them down.

Mammals, birds, insects, fish, reptiles

Pass your definitions to another group. See if you can find exceptions to the definitions you are given.

Animal Kingdom.

Work on your own. Copy this diagram. Write your favourite and your least favourite animal for each of these categories: flying, walking and swimming. Compare your choices with your partner and tell each other why you chose them.

Categories. A to Z

Work in groups of six or seven. Choose one of these categories and take turns to name a member of the category starting with the letter *a* and working through the alphabet, e.g. animals-

animal, butterfly, cat. If you can't think of one, you are out of the game. The last three left get a point. Then choose another category and repeat.

(Variation: The word has to begin with the last letter of the previous word, e.g. *giraffe, elephant, tiger..*)

Animals, food, nationalities, adjectives, rooms and furniture, clothes, verbs and others.

- Find someone in class who is wearing...

Something green, designer clothes, jeans, nylon, sandals, no socks, silk, a belt, something striped

I will tell each of you the name of someone else in class. On your own, write a description of what this person is wearing(Collect the descriptions and read them out to see how quickly the class can identify each person.)

- Point to these things, either on yourself or on another student.

zip, pocket, button, collar, laces, sleeve, hem, heel, lapel

Find out who has got:

the most zips, the deepest pockets, the brightest socks, the longest laces, the highest heels, the biggest lapels/collar, the most interesting buttons

➤ Everybody stand up. Sit down if you are wearing the things I say. The last person standing is the winner. (Read out the list one at a time. Vary or add to the list according to what your students are wearing.)

green socks, a jacket with zips, a belt, trainers, jeans, a blue shirt, a sweatshirt with a logo, high heels, a short sleeved top, something with more than six buttons, baseball cap

- **Suits you.**
- What does the rhyme ‘Red and green should never be seen; not even in a washing machine’ refer to ? (Answer: Colours which supposedly clash.)

In small groups , talk about which clothes and colours go together and which don't. Tell each other which clothes and colours suit you, and why.

- Discuss the differences between these pairs of words and phrases.

Inside out / back to front fashion / style blouse / shirt
Hat / cap to go with / to suit size / fit

➤ In pairs, find out if there is something that one of you wants to buy. Write a short conversation between a customer and a shop assistant in a shop that sells what you want. (Invite several pairs to read out their conversation.)

Conclusion

Many learners have been facing with some problems in language learning for centuries and almost all of these problems related with vocabulary knowledge. The core skill of the language is having a good word knowledge and learning word structure. Although there is not any exact

strategy that says it can help 100 % to teach vocabulary to the students, many researchers have conducted several ways such as multimedia, encyclopedias, websites and so on. It is crucial using interactive methods during the lesson for improving some visible issues of teaching vocabulary to pre-school and school students.

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